

Literature Reviews: Types, Features, Strengths, Weaknesses, and Recommendations

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ABSTRACT

Many articles present literature review as a laundry list of the writings of one author after another, which is problematic as such practice is mere tokenism and does not produce new knowledge. To fill the knowledge gap, this article responds to five research questions: 1) What are the different types of literature review? 2) What are their features? 3) What are the merits of each type of literature? 4) What are the demerits of each type of literature review? 5) What recommendations can be extended to researchers in their selection of the most appropriate type of literature review in their research articles? This article is itself a scoping literature review that aggregates different types of literature review. Methodologically, this qualitative article is a pragmatic guide for researchers in selecting the best fit review for their endeavor. Data collection is based on library search for published articles. Data analysis is based on thematic coding. Findings reveal the following: 1) There are over twenty types of literature review. 2) Each type of review is suited for qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods research. 3) Data revealed that each type of literature review has its own strengths. 4) Each also has frailties. 5) This article offered recommendations to researchers on the ways in which they could judiciously select the most appropriate literature review for their research article.

Keywords: Literature Review, Methodology, Research, Research Methodology, Research Methods

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Problem

Social Science research relies on literature review. However, researchers use different types of review inconsistently. The misuse of the wrong type of review leads to lowering the level of reliability of a study and diminishing the level of comparability across different studies.

In normative research, such as phenomenological, interpretivist, constructivist, critical, decolonial, gender, peace and conflict studies, and other related fields, authors use different ontologies, epistemologies, methodologies, and normative aims. The correct type of literature review matters, as it affects the validity of the study.

1.2. Problem Statement

1.2.1. **Conceptual Problem Statement.** There is a dearth of plain and clear guidelines for the selection of the proper review. In the worst-case scenario, most researchers do not even know the aims of a review. To compound the problem, they do not even know what type of literature review they are writing.

1.2.2. **Empirical Problem Statement.** Many researchers simply dump technical terms and other fancy words with a view to impressing readers. Often, these words are not central but peripheral at best to their concerns. Highfalutin terminology is thrown in at great measure to fill the pages without rhyme or reason. Beginner researchers struggle to match research objectives to suitable type of literature review. An erroneous methodological mismatch leads to weak qualitative (qual hereinafter) findings or quantitative (quant hereinafter) results.

1.3. Research Gap

1.3.1. **Conceptual Research Gap.** One extant typology is technical and oriented specifically to health context and library science (Grant & Booth, 2009a). Existing literature is generic and helpful for the general social sciences. However, they do not directly cater to the needs of diverse researchers, including those who have non-traditional philosophical underpinnings and are more normative than objective. Few resources explain the choices for qualitative, mixed, constructivist, critical, decolonial, and other similar types of empirical social science research.

1.3.2. **Empirical Research Gap.** There is a deficiency in published materials that enumerate diverse reviews and explain their usage and vigor in different empirical social science research settings. There are no extant materials that evaluate the advantages and demerits of each type of review. Moreover, there are no guidelines for the selection of the proper type of literature review for specific purposes.

1.4. **General Purpose of the Study.** The general purpose of this article is to provide an umbrella review of the different types of literature review.

1.5. Specific Research Questions (RQs)

1.5.1. **RQ1.** What are the various kinds of literature reviews?

1.5.2. **RQ2.** In which type of research methodology is each type of literature review best fit?

1.5.3. **RQ3.** What are the advantages of each type of literature review?

1.5.4. **RQ4.** What are the disadvantages of each type of literature review?

1.5.5. **RQ5.** What is the advice in the selection of literature review?

1.6. Specific Research Objectives (ROs)

1.6.1. **RO1.** To identify different types of literature review

1.6.2. **RO2.** To determine in which type of research methodology each type of literature review is best fit

1.6.3. **RO3.** To pinpoint the advantages of each type of literature review

1.6.4. **RO4.** To detect the disadvantages of each type of literature review

1.6.5. **RO5.** To offer advice in the selection of literature review

1.7. **Significance.** This article offers scholars and practitioners who engage in research with simple and transparent ways to detect which type of literature review fits their undertakings. This guide is suitable for all types of empirical social science research.

1.8. **Coverage of This Article**

1.8.1. **Scope.** This article presents the most used types of literature review that both social scientists and practitioners utilize.

1.8.2. **Limitations.** Due to length requirements in conference proceedings, this work focuses only on providing a cursory list of the various reviews, their characteristics, strong points, weaknesses, and recommendations on selections.

1.8.3. **Delimitations.** The author of this paper does not examine outcomes of the application of each type of literature review. Readers need further to consult research methodology textbooks for detailed and in-depth treatment of each literature review type.

2. **LITERATURE REVIEW**

2.1. **Overview.** Firstly, this section provides a discussion of the concept of literature review. Secondly, it gives a scoping of the existing literature that maps the different types of literature review.

2.2. **Conceptual Literature Review**

2.2.1. **What Literature Review Is.** Literature review, when well written, is a well-organized way in which the authors primarily portray the current knowledge base. The purpose of which is to impart knowledge about the meanings of key terms, empirical evidentiary findings or results, agreements among authors, disagreements, contributions, shortcomings, as well as gaps (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Thereafter, researcher provide a justification for the need of conducting their study (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

2.2.2. **How to Write Literature Review.** Authors need to sew all ideas together to tell a compelling story about a given topic. Researchers search for sources, such as academic books, journals, and gray literature such as reliable news sources and governmental and non-governmental organization (NGO) reports. Authors organize together analogous ideas and concepts to form themes with a view to constructing arguments, revealing patterns, and identifying gaps. See Figure below.

Figure 1: Purpose of a Literature Review

2.2.3. **Outputs.** The outputs of literature review are varied. In general, literature review yields the following outputs (Torraco, 2005a): a new model, taxonomy, research agenda, meta-theory, and new knowledge. Specifically for old or mature topics, a literature review supplies new perspectives or the opportunity for reconceptualization. For new or emerging topics, literature review lays out a new model or a new research agenda. A literature review which produces a typology can serve as the research methodology of a concept or review paper (Shahsavari & Alamolhoda, 2019).

2.3. **Scoping Literature Review.** Gathering from different publications, there are at least twenty types of literature review. The most important publication identified fourteen types of literature reviews (Grant & Booth, 2009a). Other documents specified five types (Gangadhar, 2024), seven review types (Taherdoost, 2023), six types (Franco et al., 2025), nine types of reviews (Paré et al., 2015a). There are important sources on how to write

integrative literature reviews (Torraco, 2005b, 2016a). From the major publications on the listing of reviews, I gathered and presented them in alphabetical order in the Findings of this article for easy access.

2.4. **Gaps in the Existing Literature.** The sources cited above only provide general descriptions for use in empirical social sciences, especially for research which is more objective than subjective. However, they do not explain which type of research methodology each review best fits. Moreover, they do not provide guidelines especially for use in normative social sciences, such as critical, intersectional, decolonial, feminist, and peace studies. There is a gap that this article fills. This article produced a simplified analysis on the different types and uses of reviews. The aim is to empower beginner and junior researchers in the selection and choice of which type of literature review they use for specific purposes.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. **Type of Research.** This article uses review of literature as the research methodology to provide a list of commonly used reviews, their uses, strengths, weaknesses, and recommendations (Shahsavari & Alamolhoda, 2019).

3.2. **Philosophy.** Based on pragmatic research philosophy, this article analyzes the ways in which each review type functions across divergent epistemological and normative research agenda. It seeks to identify the best fit for specific types of research methodology, weighing their benefits and setbacks.

3.3. **Research Design.** This descriptive qualitative paper identified and selected different types of literature review.

3.4. **Research Strategy.** This work is a scoping review.

3.5. **Research Approach.** As a qualitative article, this work inductively analyzed, critiqued, and synthesized the existing literature.

3.6. **Data Collection.** Here, data about the different review types are based on documents gathered through desk research.

3.7. **Data Analysis.** After reading the different review articles, I took analytic memos and identified patterns. Thereafter, I systematically coded the materials, labeling them after capturing their meanings. I listed, named, and grouped the codes to develop broad themes, connecting them to the research questions and presenting them in the research findings.

4. FINDINGS

4.1. Analysis

4.1.1. **RQ1.** Some of the different types of reviews are the following: argumentative, bibliometric or citation, conceptual, content, critical, expert or consensus, discourse, historical or chronological, integrative, mapping, meta-analysis, meta-ethnography, meta-synthesis or qualitative evidence, methodological or technical, mixed-methods, narrative or traditional, policy, rapid, realist, science mapping, scoping, state of the art, state of evidence or evidence mapping, state-of-the-field or comprehensive mapping, systematic, thematic, theoretical, and umbrella.

4.1.2. **RQ2, RQ3, RQ4, RQ5.** Below are responses to research questions two to five, culling information from key published listings of literature reviews. Due to page limitations, I present the answers for the research questions 2, 3, 4, and 5 in few words in a typology in the Table below.

Table 1: Typology of Literature Review

No.	Review Types	RQ1: Features	RQ2: Best Fit	RQ3: Strengths	RQ4: Weaknesses	RQ5: Recommendations
1.	Argumentative (Snyder, 2019)	Persuasive arguments	Qual	Useful for pro and con debates	Selection bias	When necessary to take sides in normative discussions and position papers
2.	Bibliometric or Citation (Donthu et al., 2021)	Numerical mapping of scholarly materials	Quant	Reveal latest trends, influential researchers	Dependent on indexed English language works	Lay of the land of a given field, gaps, and research agenda henceforth
3.	Conceptual (Jaakkola, 2020)	Defines concepts	Qual	Keywords are clarified	Interpretivist; No empirical basis	Used to create a conceptual framework
4.	Content (White & Marsh, 2006)	Count how many times keywords were used	Quant, Mixed	Numerical evidence of frequency	Shallow patterns in figures only	
5.	Critical (Grant & Booth, 2009b)	Questions power and authority	Qual	Reveal ideology; Contextual; listen to marginalized voices	Subjective; interpretivist	Valuable in normative research
6.	Discourse (Wodak & Meyer, 2016)	Debates among multiple voices	Qual	Reveal interaction, power, contestation, or co-construction of ideas	Equally valid subjective views presented	Reveal the contending voices in society
7.	Expert or Consensus (Murphy et al., 1998)	Summary of what experts say	Mixed	Speedy; action oriented	Individual biases; no generalizable proof	Use when no proof is available
8.	Historical or Chronological (Torraco, 2005a)	Genesis and development of a given concept or phenomenon	Qual	Longitudinal view	Access to sources; Claims are not neutral	Tracing policy progress
9.	Integrative (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005)	Consider the breadth and synthesize	Qual	Analysis, critique, synthesis, and next steps	Time consuming; overreach	Generate new ideas
10.	Mapping (Grant & Booth, 2009c)	Visual thematic classification	Mixed	Useful for funding agencies	Lacks deep synthesis	Useful with templates
11.	Meta-Analysis (Borenstein, 2013)	Pool the size of effects statistically	Quant	Precision in the estimation of effects	Comparable information are needed;	Investigate several comparable research

					heterogeneous data are not useful	
12.	Meta-Ethnography (Noblit & Hare, 1997)	Subjective synthesis of field studies	Qual	Grounded theory production	Time consuming	Inter- and cross-cultural theory building
13.	Meta-Synthesis or Qualitative Evidence (Sandelowski & Barroso, 2007)	Creates new key terms from a host of qualitative studies	Qual	Deeper understanding of multiple voices	Subjectivist; Not comparable	Accumulation of lived experiences
14.	Methodological or Technical (Booth et al., 2016)	Centers on research tools	Quant; Mixed	Improves measuring variables and comparative research	Limited in scope	Good for refining operational indicators and system of measurement
15.	Mixed-Methods (Hong et al., 2018)	Intentional integration of both qual and quant studies	Mixed	Holistic	Complex	Thorough appraisal of programs
16.	Narrative or Traditional (Green et al., 2006)	General synopsis; storytelling; one dominant voice	Qual	Ease; Context matters; meaning making of one main voice	Cherry Picking; Subjective; Not systematic	Many researchers commonly use this
17.	Policy or Evidence to Policy (Oliver et al., 2014)	Concentrate on documents and evidence related to policies	Mixed	Actionable	Ideological bias of funders; prescriptive	Advise policy and law making
18.	Rapid	Quick review	Mixed	When speedy response is needed	Danger of prejudice; not thorough	Practical to respond to calamities
19.	Realist (Pawson et al., 2005)	Investigates the situation, intervention mechanisms, and outcomes	Both	Clarifies which actors gain from a given approach for what reason	Complex	Used for difficult interventions such as peace building
20.	Science-Mapping (Cobo et al., 2011)	Visualization of thematic groupings	Quant	Analyze and discover big data trends	Heavy on the use of databases and scientific software use	Important in producing generalizable statements
21.	Scoping (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Munn et	Map the width of current knowledge	Qual; Mixed	Wide-ranging	Lacks depth; No valuation	Lay of the land of emergent issues

	al., 2018; Peters et al., 2015, 2015; Pham et al., 2014; Tricco et al., 2015)					
22.	State of the Art (Paré et al., 2015b)	Cite and count latest data and trend	Both	Objectively map what is currently known and influential; Applicable to the current situation	Overlook deeper causes; Mostly English language	Useful for immediate use
23.	State of Evidence or Evidence Mapping (Miake-Lye et al., 2016)	Synthesize available data	Quant; Mixed	Priority setting for policy inputs	Too technical for neophytes	Useful for establishing plans
24.	State of the Field or Comprehensive Mapping (Grant & Booth, 2009d)	Broad investigation into the status of and trends in a given field	Mixed	Within-field goings on	More broad than deep; time consuming; access to sources	Program evaluation, planning, and development
25.	Systematic (Moher et al., 2009)	Comprehensive search using predetermined protocols	Qual, Quant, Mixed	Rigor; replicability	Only indexed academic materials; gray literature exclusion	Best overview of a given topic, useful for policy prioritization
26.	Thematic (Braun & Clarke, 2006)	Cluster research into thematic groups	Qual	Clarity of distinct themes	Subjective biases; Not replicable	Explain emerging themes
27.	Theoretical (Torraco, 2016a)	Explain variables in a theory or theories	Quant	Explains independent, dependent, and other variables	Only deductively derived	Useful for theoretical application
28.	Umbrella (Aromataris et al., 2015)	The parent of reviews that synthesize numerous systematic ones	Mixed	Exhibit high degree of evidence for use in policymaking	Biases in previous studies are compounded	Helpful for policy synopsis

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1. **Findings in Relation to Literature.** There is no best review. Rather, there are reviews that best fit certain types of research questions and methodology: qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods. The proper match boosts validity in social research. Transparent selection criteria decrease author bias and error in research.

4.2.2. Unexpected Findings

4.2.2.1. The various kinds of reviews are not mutually exclusive. They overlap. In fact, different types of reviews can be combined to create hybrids, such as narrative systematic reviews, theoretical and conceptual reviews, and content and discourse reviews.

- 4.2.2.2. Most types are applicable to both qualitative and quantitative research. Some types are only applicable exclusively for quantitative or qualitative studies. For example, meta-analytic literature reviews use quantitative design that relies on statistical estimates.
- 4.2.3. **Limitations.** The list of reviews is not cast in stone, as it is continually evolving.
- 4.2.4. **Contributions.** This article furnishes a simple but wide-ranging guide for selecting the types of reviews for appropriate research methodology and epistemology.
- 4.2.5. **Who Benefits?**
- 4.2.5.1. Early career academics or apprentice researchers benefit from using easier types, such as narrative review.
- 4.2.5.2. Policymakers, governmental organizations, NGOs, and private business decision makers benefit from rigorous reviews. For example, systematic and umbrella reviews are solidly grounded on evidence and thus trusted materials which can serve as inputs for policy making.
- 4.2.5.3. Scholars engaged in normative research, such as decolonial, social justice, gender, and peace studies benefit from critical reviews as they allow for constructivist, interpretivist, and prescriptive epistemology and critique. See Figure below.

Figure 2: Beneficiaries of Literature Review

- 4.2.6. **At What Cost?**
- 4.2.6.1. In argumentative, critical, chronological or historical, discourse, expert or consensus, meta-ethnographic, narrative, and rapid reviews, there are built-in subjectivities and biases.
- 4.2.6.2. In systematic reviews, gray literature, such as personal correspondence and NGO reports are excluded.
- 4.2.6.3. In systematic, methodological or technical, meta-analytic, science mapping, umbrella reviews, studies are resource intensive, as researchers need access to specialized software, funding, and meta-data databases. See Figure below.

Figure 3: Challenges in Literature Review

5. CONCLUSION

5.1. Summary

- 5.1.1. There are over twenty to thirty types of literature reviews. They must be selected properly for use in qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods research. Each has strengths and weaknesses. Some reviews are recommended for specific types of

empirical social science investigation, while others are largely appropriate for most research work.

5.2. Conclusion

5.2.1. Knowledge of review types serves as a navigator through your research journey. They have specific aims, guidelines, and ability to persuade the end users. Select the correct review so that your research is credible. Identify and explain the reasons for which you choose a specific type of review in your work and proceed step by step, in that way you are transparent about the inclusion of materials in your study and portray rigor. For decision makers, data gathered from the appropriate literature serves to guide policy agenda which is evidence-based and data-driven.

5.2.2. Research questions, not convenience, guides the type of literature and methodology that is best fit for your study. Structure your research so that your knowledge contributes to agenda that promotes social good and positive social transformation.

5.3. **Recommendations.** This article recommends certain types of literature review for different levels of research skills as well as for normative research. See Figure below.

Figure 4: Recommendations for Use of Review Types

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